

DETERIORATING STANDARDS OF GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Education plays the important and foremost role as an effective instrument for achievement and survival. Purposeful education enables the individual to understand and study the real-life situation and to develop an opportunity for creating confidence and provide a strong base for rational and value-oriented and nation-building progress to get this education we need to go to schools. Nextly, teachers are responsible for the pupils' education or educating them at all levels. Now there are two types of schools; government schools and private schools. Here in these, we are talking about government schools and their deteriorating standards. Why government schools are deteriorating standards? So some major issues are infrastructure issues, teacher issues, poor quality education, syllabus issues, and many more. For which measure steps are to be taken to improve the quality as well standards of government schools. We have overall seen the issues and the steps to be taken. Currently, government school children's learning outcome is minimum, and their sense of living, way of talking, and overall personality are different from that of private schools which also needs to be focused on. Proper sanitation and cleanliness should be maintained in government schools which will help children attend their schools regularly. Several years back people who were not economically sound, and their children were unable to get an education so the government took the initiative to provide schooling to all children between 6-14 years by forming an act that is right to education act. The right to education has now become the fundamental right and is included in part III of the Indian constitution under article 21-A. This was done in the case of **Mohini Jain vs. the state of Karnataka**. The Supreme Court division bench decided this case. Justice comprising of **Kuldip Singh and R.M Sahai** held that:-

“Right to education is the essence of the right to life and directly flow and interlinked with it and life living with dignity can only be assured when there is a significant role of education.”

Later examined by five judges' bench in **J.P. Unnikrishnan v. State of Andhra Pradesh** and held that:-

“Right to education means citizen has the right to call up the state to provide the facilities of education to them in according to the financial capacity.”

The above-mentioned cases list the right to education to be in part III being as a fundamental right.

Some more cases that enumerate the right to education as a Fundamental right like the case of State **Board of Secondary and Higher Education vs. K.S. Gandhi** and case **Bandhua Mukti Morcha, etc v. Union of India**.

AN OVERVIEW

The Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 inserted Article 21-A in the Constitution of India to provide free and compulsory education to all children in the age group of six to fourteen (6-14) years as a Fundamental Right. Every child has a right to complete full-time elementary education. Act casts on free education and compulsory education which means each child residing in India should at least complete its elementary education whether economically sound or not. Compulsory education is the obligation of the appropriate government to provide free elementary education. Free means that no child shall be liable to pay any kind of fee or charges or expenses which may prevent him or her from pursuing and completing elementary education. Now let's focus on our main topic which is the deteriorating standards of government schools no doubt that government schools are providing free education or at a minimum fee but the standards and quality of education in government schools are being questioned because of the deteriorating learning levels of children. If made a

comparison between private schools and government schools learning outcomes and way of living is more in private school than that in government school.

In recent years, the Government of India has become increasingly interested in the relationship between resources devoted and student learning outcomes. The most cited is the Annual Survey of Education Report (ASER), conducted by a non-governmental organization called Pratham. According to ASER, in the last five years learning has deteriorated in government schools whereas if talk about the private school can do better in both reading as well as arithmetic skills. (ASER 2017). When we talk about learning outcomes it immediately and ultimately generates about teachers. Are they responsible for the same? If not, then what are the issues responsible for it?

CHALLENGES FACED BY GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS

Infrastructure issues:

Most government schools do not have proper infrastructures like playground, classroom, and blackboard and the most important government school lacks proper sanitation, drinking water, and toilets. The school environment is so suffocating that many dropouts from the school so the dropout rate is also high. Due to a lack of proper sanitation parents may think that their child may get some disease.

Teacher issues:

Teachers' professional development is a weak area in government schools. The absenteeism of teachers in these schools is very high even after paying a much higher salary they cheat the government and also fail to perform their duty as teachers. Sadly no actions are being taken to prevent this. The casualty of teachers also leads to lowering the standard and quality of government schools.

Poor quality of education:

The major problem is the difference in the syllabus of government schools and private schools which makes the quality of schools better than government schools. Several reports say that about 70% of students studying in government schools are not able to cope to which they are admitted. On the other hand, private schools offer experienced staff, efficient learning methodologies, and good infrastructure which are driving away from government schools.

Syllabus issue:

After making a comparison between the syllabus of two that is private and government schools syllabi of private schools are more effective and efficient than government schools when we talk about any competitive examination we had to go through the private school's syllabus i.e. NCERT.

Poor implementation of the RTE Act:

Section 29 of the right to education narrates what kind of education every child must learn. No government school is complying with that. Government should focus on government schools.

Corruption:

Officers in education departments are being managed to false file reports about the working condition of schools. Nowadays government schools also charge a minimum amount of fees from the students but no activities are being taken.

Gender bias:

According to the ASER report by Pratham in 2020, parents prefer private schools for the education of boys while girl students are primarily sent to government schools to get basic education as they think girls are meant to be a housewife or they'll go to someone else house.

Caste bias:

There are several discriminations made regarding the caste system. On one side our constitution talks about equality and on another side, it has reservations for the caste-like OBC ST SC NT.

A Better Option (Private Schools) than Government Schools:

As we say English is most important in today's world and private school brands in the English medium so it has driven parents away from government schools thinking about.

STEPS TO BE TAKEN TO IMPROVE THE STANDARDS AND QUALITY

Maintain infrastructure:

A good and well-maintained building with lots of space, infrastructures like furniture, classrooms with Good ventilation, playgrounds, extracurricular activities, computer labs, and most important clean toilet with proper sanitation, and accessible drinking water will make students attend school regularly.

Extracurricular activities:

Extracurricular activities are also equally important for a child to develop life skills and personality. When we made a comparison between private school children and government school children there is a vast difference in both of them whether in the living sense, talking sense, way of behavior, or in any ways.

Quality of teachers and teaching:

Teachers and/or their way of teaching are directly responsible for student development. There should be modern aid teachings, tools, and methodologies

integrated with technologies that make people interested in taking up teaching as a profession and also make the student interested in attending school.

The syllabus should be changed:

When we prepare for any competitive exam we need to refer to NCERT but government schools do not have NCERT. The syllabus is limited in government schools.

In today's modern world education is most important for survival in this technological world. After knowing these then also government schools' standards are deteriorating day by day. We need to take initiative for the improvement of standards and quality not only us but also government should check over the schools. The government has to take many measures such as a healthy environment, change in syllabus, infrastructures, and methodologies which will make the student interested in attending regular college will make our generation productive and will also help in development.

LIMITATION TO RIGHT TO EDUCATION

It provides free compulsory education between 6-14 but accordingly in today's situation elementary education is not sufficient for survival. Till 14 has no value in itself. Children below 6 years are not covered under this act. At the time of admission, many documents such as birth certificate, BPL, and caste certificate are required which left out orphans of these beneficiaries act.

If a student is capable and is a meritorious student but not economically sound tries to take admission in government schools but due to reservations he/she may not get the admission so just because of reservation he/she is left behind and also not capable to apply at private schools.

On one side our constitution says about equality and makes hyped of equality and another side it talks about reservations. It's just the act says to educate the children between 6-14 more focus is being given to the statistics of

RTE rather than the quality of learning. Nowadays government schools are also taking fees from students. Funding issues government should take care of.

THE CONCLUSION

We can conclude that Education is most important no doubt but government schools standards are lowering day by day which makes outcome level of future generation very people. People afford government schools because they are not capable to study in private institutions but if the situation arises that government schools standards are getting lowered and quality education is not available parents will drive their children from education and make them their helping hands like earlier which will ultimately affect our future economy and development. So the government should focus on government schools and institutions so that it leads to a productive future.

Also, the major problem faced by the government is funding issues for that not only the government but also the citizens should make sure of it that government schools have enough funds to make effective government schooling. Human Rights education should be a basic part of the educational system not only in the school but also in the university curricula.

Teaching the basic principle of non-discrimination and the fundamental rights and freedoms shows that every human being has these rights and freedoms. Education is a significant step to achieving all other basic human rights. Education can help decrease poverty, reduce social inequalities, empower women and others marginalized, bring down discrimination, and finally help individuals live life to their fullest potential. Government school teachers should also take initiative to make a child more and more productive and should not only focus on giving elementary education according to RTE.

Government school staff should change their attitude and not only run behind the money but should think about the nation and child's future. Should maintain proper sanitation and cleanliness, so that it would prevent them from suffering

from the disease. One most important fact is teachers behave with the student in a way which is not good comparatively of private schools teachers are much better than them it's just according to family background behavior which is very wrong and yes this is a bitter reality.

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